

The MED-CORDEX ensemble future climate projections for the Mediterranean Sea: impacts of the high resolution and ocean-atmosphere coupling

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Objectives:

- Is the climate change response consistent in all the models?
- Is there a significant impact of the higher resolution in the RCMs?
- Is there a significant impact of the ocean-atmosphere coupling?

In this presentation: 28 **baseline simulations**. 14 historical (10 RCM, 4 ARCM), 14 RCP 8.5 scenario runs (10 RCM, 4 ARCM).

Institution	RCM (8)	ARCM (4)	GCM (7)	Scenario	Short Name
CNRM	CNRM-RCSM4		CNRM-CM5	RCP 8.5	CNRM-CM5
	CNRM-RCSM6	CNRM-ALADIN63	CNRM-ESM2-1	SSP 5-85	CNRM-ESM2
GERICS-AWI	GERICS-AWI-ROM25	REMO25	MPI-ESM-LR	RCP 8.5	AWI-25-MPI
	GERICS-AWI-ROM50	REMO50	MPI-ESM-LR	RCP 8.5	AWI-50-MPI
LMD	LMD-LMDZNEMOMED8		IPSL-CM5A-MR	RCP 8.5	LMD-IPSL
			MPI-ESM-MR	RCP 8.5	LMD-MPI
			CNRM-CM5	RCP 8.5	LMD-CNRM
U. Belgrade	EBU-POM2	EBU	MPI-ESM-LR	RCP 8.5	UBEL-MPI
CMCC	CMCC-CCLM4		CMCC-CM	RCP 8.5	CMCC-CMCC
GUF	CLMcom-GUF-CCLM5		EC-EARTH	RCP 8.5	GUF-ECEARTH

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- Analysis of the climate change signal of SST and atmospheric variables at the surface level

Climate Change (CC) signal computed as the difference between the averages of the last 30 years of the projection (2070-2100) and the last 30 years of the historical period (1976-2005).

$$\text{CC signal} = \text{average}(2070-2100) - \text{average}(1976-2005)$$

SST and Air temperature increase

AWI-25-MPI SST CC signal (°C)

- All the simulations show a warming of the sea surface **between 2.5 and 4 °C** on average.
- The Air T average increase is around **30% higher** than for the SST.

AWI-25-MPI Air T CC signal (°C)

SST and Air temperature increase

Decrease of the net heat losses
towards the atmosphere (heat gain)

AWI-25-MPI SST CC signal (°C)

AWI-25-MPI Net Surface Heat Flux CC signal (W/m²)

AWI-25-MPI Air T CC signal (°C)

➤ Decrease in the net heat loss (average 0.2 – 4.3 W/m²) with high spatial variability → the atmosphere is cooling less the sea and even starting to warm it for some models.

SST and Air temperature increase

Decrease of the net heat losses
towards the atmosphere (heat gain)

Decrease of Precipitation

AWI-25-MPI SST CC signal (°C)

AWI-25-MPI Net Surface Heat Flux CC signal (W/m²)

AWI-25-MPI Precipitation CC signal (mm/d)

AWI-25-MPI Air T CC signal (°C)

➤ Precipitation decreases in all RCMs
(average -0.1 – -0.4 mm/d).

➤ Decrease in the net heat loss (average 0.2 – 4.3 W/m²) with high spatial variability → the atmosphere is cooling less the sea and even starting to warm it for some models.

Consistency among all the models

SST CC signal averaged over de Med Sea

Net Surface Heat Flux CC signal averaged over de Med Sea

Air T CC signal averaged over de Med Sea

Precipitation CC signal averaged over de Med Sea

Impact of the resolution

RCM

GCM

AWI-ROM25 average historical SST & Air T signal (°C)

MPI-ESM-LR average historical SST & Air T signal (°C)

Vs

Differences between the RCMs and GCMs CC signals

AWI-ROM25 vs MPI-ESM-LR SST dCC signals (°C)

- The average SST CC signal is slightly stronger in the GCMs (+ 0.2 °C on average).
- Significant differences between RCM and GCM SST in the spatial structures.
- The air T signal is clearly stronger in the GCMs (+ 0.4 °C on average).
- More pronounced differences in specific regions as the Adriatic or the Gulf of Lions, reaching 1 °C on average in these sub-basins for some models.

AWI-ROM25 vs MPI-ESM-LR Air T dCC signals (°C)

Air T CC signal averaged over the Adriatic Sea

Differences between the RCMs and GCMs CC signals

AWI-ROM25 vs MPI-ESM-LR SST dCC signals (°C)

➤ The higher SST, air temperature and the consequent increase in the heat gain in the GCMs are translated in a generalized higher reduction of the precipitation over the basin (+0.2 mm/d on average, although very dependent on the model).

AWI-ROM25 vs MPI-ESM-LR Air T dCC signals (°C)

AWI-ROM25 vs MPI-ESM-LR Precipitation dCC signals (mm/d)

Impact of the coupling

RCM

ARCM

High resolution atmospheric model

High resolution atmospheric model

Feedback between
ocean and atmosphere

Vs

SST boundary condition
from GCM, no feedback

High resolution ocean model

Low resolution SST from GCM

Differences between the RCMs and ARCMs CC signals

AWI-ROM25 vs REMO25 SST dCC signals (°C)

AWI-ROM25 vs REMO25 Air T dCC signals (°C)

- The average SST CC differences are similar to the differences with the GCMs, as expected because the ARCMs use GCMs as boundary condition.
- Significant changes in the spatial structures.
- The air T signal differences are not as pronounced as with the GCMs, but still significant for the spatial structures.

Impact of the coupling

Differences between the RCMs and ARCMs CC signals

AWI-ROM25 vs REMO25 SST dCC signals (°C)

AWI-ROM25 vs REMO25 HFLS dCC signals (W/m²)

AWI-ROM25 vs REMO25 Air T dCC signals (°C)

Latent Heat Flux CC signal averaged over the Med Sea

- ARCMs show stronger latent HF signals than both RCMs and GCMs → more evaporation to compensate the higher SST increase from the GCMs boundary condition at the sea surface.
- Also higher humidity increase in the ARCMs (not shown) → SST – Air - T gradient and latent heat flux differences.

Impact of the coupling

Differences between the RCMs and ARCMs CC signals

AWI-ROM25 vs REMO25 SST dCC signals (°C)

AWI-ROM25 vs REMO25 precipitation dCC signals (mm/d)

➤ Stronger precipitation decrease in ARCM. As a consequence of the differences in the heat gain.

AWI-ROM25 vs REMO25 Air T dCC signals (°C)

Precipitation CC signal averaged over the Med Sea

Summary

Consistency in the CC
respond of all the
simulations for the variables
analyzed.

Increase in the SST and
the Air T

Decrease of the net heat
losses towards the
atmosphere (heat gain)

Decrease of
Precipitation

Impact of the high
resolution
RCM vs GCM

Lower SST and Air T CC
signals in the RCM

Very significant impact on
the spatial structures

Higher reduction
of precipitation in
the GCMs (model
dependent)

Impact of ocean-
atmosphere coupling
RCM vs ARCM

SST CC signals differences
similar to GCM. Smaller
differences in the Air T.

Very significant impact on
the evaporative heat
losses (higher in ARCMs)

Higher reduction
of precipitation in
the ARCMs

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Extra slides

Med-CORDEX

International initiative that aims at developing **fully coupled high resolution Regional Climate Models (RCMs)** for the **Mediterranean basin**, as part of the global **CORDEX** initiative.

Institutions

- CMCC
- CNRM
- ENEA
- GERICS-AWI
- GUF
- LMD
- U. Belgrade

Baseline atm – ocean
coupled simulations

33 historical and
multi-scenario
simulations

Climate change studies
in the Mediterranean
basin

Temperature anomalies of the water column from 1950 to 2100 (°C)
(from Soto-Navarro et al 2020)

See Darmaraki et al., Clim. Dyn. (2019) and Soto-Navarro et al., Clim. Dyn. (2020) for details

Surface heat flux components

AWI-25-MPI Net Shortwave Radiation CC signal (W/m^2) AWI-25-MPI Latent Heat Flux CC signal (W/m^2)

AWI-25-MPI Net Longwave Radiation CC signal (W/m^2) AWI-25-MPI Sensible Heat Flux CC signal (W/m^2)

Heat flux positive downwards (towards the ocean)

- Increase of the net **shortwave** radiation → reduction in the cloud cover and aerosol concentration
- Increase of the net **longwave** radiation → atmospheric warming due to GHG (among other factors)
- Increase of the **sensible** heat flux → due to the increase in the difference between the Air and Sea Temp
- Decrease of the **latent** heat flux, meaning an **increase** in the heat loss due to **evaporation** → the only negative term (tend compensate). **Modulated by wind**

AWI-25-MPI Wind Intensity CC signal (m/s)

Humidity and clouds cover

AWI-25-MPI Specific Humidity CC signal (g/kg)

AWI-25-MPI Clouds cover CC signal (%)

- Increase of the specific humidity due to the increase of the evaporation and atmospheric warming (Clausius-Clapeyron)
- General decrease in the cloud cover → Med climate is less prone to convection in the future

Differences between the RCMs and GCMs CC signals

AWI-ROM25 vs MPI-ESM-LR SST dCC signals (°C)

AWI-ROM25 vs MPI-ESM-LR NSWR dCC signals (W/m²)

AWI-ROM25 vs MPI-ESM-LR HFLS dCC signals (w/m²)

Heat flux positive downwards (towards the ocean)

AWI-ROM25 vs MPI-ESM-LR Air T dCC signals (°C)

- RCMs signals weaker than GCMs for shortwave rad → higher reduction of the cloud cover in the GCMs and not inclusion of aerosols in all RCMs
- RCMs signal weaker than GCMs for latent heat flux → more evaporation in the GCMs due to higher SST increase
- RCMs sensible heat flux signals are stronger than for the GCMs in 5 of the 7 simulations (not shown) → stronger gradient between SST and Air-T in RCMs
- No consistent difference between RCMs and GCMs in Precipitation

Spatial averages of the CC signal over land

Specific humidity CC signal

Cloud cover CC signal

Precipitation CC signal

- As for the Med, general increase of humidity over land, but of lower magnitude. Higher in the RCMs and even more in the ARMs because of the HFSL differences
- Again, general decrease in the clouds cover, lower than over sea.
- Over land 3 of the 4 GCMs show a stronger decrease of the clouds cover. The differences between RCMs and ARCMs are no significant.
- The precipitation behavior is not as clear over land than over sea.
- All models show a very small average signal, but very high spatial variability.
- Clear diff between GCM response and RCM/ARCM.
- RCM seem to be drier than ARCM → change in land-sea contrast

The land region is too large and affected by different and complex processes on each region. More accurate results will be obtained when analyzing the land-sea interaction over specific land regions instead of the whole domain.